

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN INTEGRATING FORMAL, INFORMAL, AND HIDDEN CURRICULA

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Introduction

Tanner and Tanner (1980) defined curriculum as “the planned and guided learning experiences and intended outcomes, formulated through the systematic reconstruction of knowledge and experiences under the auspices of the school, for the learners' continuous and wilful growth in personal social competence.” Curriculum can also be viewed as the comprehensive educational framework that encompasses everything schools do to shape learners into what society expects them to become. It represents the core ideas, goals, and objectives of teaching and learning in schools, helping students integrate into society and contribute to its progress. However, education extends beyond the formal curriculum taught in classrooms. When planning and instructing, teachers must consider the formal, informal, and hidden curricula, as these three components have distinct yet interconnected effects on students' learning experiences and outcomes. The formal curriculum consists of structured content mandated by educational authorities, while the informal curriculum involves learning that occurs through social interactions and extracurricular activities. The hidden curriculum, on the other hand, comprises the implicit values, attitudes, and behaviours that students acquire from their educational environment. This essay explores how educators incorporate these different types of curricula into their lesson planning and instructional strategies.

TYPES OF CURRICULA

1. **Formal Curriculum:** This is a structured document provided to teachers to guide their teaching. It serves as a framework in the form of a syllabus and typically includes objectives, subject matter, learning experiences, teaching techniques, assessment methods, and recommended reading materials.
2. **Informal Curriculum:** This refers to learning experiences gained through co-curricular or extracurricular activities outside the formal classroom setting. Unlike the formal curriculum, informal learning involves non-academic activities that enhance the understanding of formal content.
3. **Hidden Curriculum:** This consists of lessons that students learn from the school environment, organizational structure, and the behaviour and attitudes of teachers and administrators (Longstreet & Shane, 1993). The hidden curriculum is neither written nor explicitly intended but is learned through unconscious values, beliefs, norms, behaviours, and assumptions. It operates alongside the formal and informal curriculum and significantly influences students' learning and behaviour.

How Teachers Take Curriculum into Account in Planning and Teaching

A school cannot function without a curriculum, as it serves as the foundation for education. The curriculum is essential to a school's existence, providing direction for teachers and students alike. Teachers play a crucial role in implementing the curriculum in classrooms, making it a vital tool in both planning and teaching.

- **Formal Curriculum:** Teachers plan lessons to meet state educational guidelines, ensuring that all necessary knowledge is imparted to students. They break down the curriculum into topics, sub-topics, and lessons, allowing for flexibility in pacing to accommodate the allotted time. By structuring their teaching, teachers ensure that learning objectives are met within the given timeframe.
- **Informal Curriculum:** This encompasses unplanned learning experiences that occur within the classroom, school compound, or during student interactions (UNESCO, 2004). Teachers facilitate informal learning by encouraging students to join various school clubs

and societies. Extracurricular activities, such as sports, drama, and debate clubs, may be scheduled during break time, after school, on weekends, or during holidays. These activities provide students with a better understanding of concepts taught in the classroom.

- **Hidden Curriculum:** The hidden curriculum complements the formal curriculum and plays a key role in students' academic, vocational, and social development. Schools often enforce certain hidden curricula. For example, in Nigeria, speaking one's mother tongue is prohibited in many schools, which may inadvertently send a message that the school system does not value native cultures and languages. Teachers play a vital role in addressing such issues and ensuring that students develop a balanced perspective.

In conclusion, teachers integrate the formal, informal, and hidden curriculum to provide a well-rounded learning experience. The **formal curriculum**, comprising official subjects and assessments, is structured through scheduled lessons and taught using lectures, discussions, and evaluations. The **informal curriculum**, which includes learning gained through extracurricular activities and social interactions, is integrated through real-world applications and interactive experiences. The **hidden curriculum**, which consists of unwritten lessons related to values, attitudes, and behaviours, is reinforced through an inclusive classroom environment and modeled by teachers. By balancing these three aspects, teachers help students achieve academic success, develop social skills, and grow emotionally.

Reference

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